

Tomale.AI:

Bringing children's stories to life with AI

Innovate
UK

BridgeAI

CASE STUDY

Tomale.AI

Bringing children's stories to life with AI

Research from the National Literacy Trust shows children's reading interest in the UK is at an all-time low, with most preferring TV, gaming and social media to reading. Closer to home, every parent knows the magic of a bedtime story – but also the frustration of reading the same book for what seems like the hundredth time. These stories become fond but distant memories for both parents and children.

UK-based business [Tomale.AI](#) aims to change that by helping families create personalised storybooks in minutes using the power of generative AI, immortalising cherished memories while fostering creativity and reading engagement from an early age.

Founded by Kyle Burke, Tomale.AI is part of a new wave of creative AI startups supported by Innovate UK's BridgeAI programme. Through the programme, Kyle worked with an Independent Scientific Advisor, Dr Jennifer Williams of the University of Southampton, to explore how generative AI models could be made to behave more consistently and reliably – without impacting on their inherent creativity.

“Our big mission is to build a love of reading in every child,”

Kyle Burke,
Founder, Tomale.AI

Credit: Tomale.ai

Tomale.AI's platform enables users to produce illustrated children's stories from simple text prompts with an AI assistant, personalised to each user's preferences. Behind the scenes, the app combines large language models for storytelling with image-generation models for illustration, creating unique, ready-to-share books.

While the creative potential is huge, developing reliable AI pipelines for both text and imagery proved technically demanding. Jennifer's work focused on helping Tomale.AI address specific AI-related technical challenges, including tailoring the generated text to particular age groups and – crucially – ensuring consistency between images of the stories' characters.

"We had really been struggling to replicate a character's appearance across each page of the story, and across multiple separate stories," says Kyle. "Or, if the story is about a trip to Atlantis for example, to get the model to infer the character would need to be wearing scuba gear." Furthermore, Kyle was keen to explore how to retain the key characteristics of a character across multiple artwork styles, such as watercolour painting, wax crayons or Japanese anime.

"Working with Jennifer through the ISA offer has been really valuable. She helped me understand the technology at a much deeper level and pointed me in the right direction when I got stuck. It's given me a clearer idea of what's possible with AI, and provided a roadmap to upskill myself to leverage this technology and implement my creative vision."

Kyle Burke,
Founder, Tomale.AI

Credit: Written & illustrated by
Grandma Jane and Tomale.ai

Kyle adds: “Jennifer has been fantastic at talking to me through the various available techniques to improve this aspect of the product. We settled on a technique called Low-Rank Adaptation, or LoRA, which allows us to fine-tune the model to learn specific visual rules and cues. Working with Jennifer has not only improved my technical knowledge but also given me a more rigorous, research-inspired approach to how we develop the product.”

Looking beyond the launch of version 1 of the app, Kyle sees vast potential for Tomale.AI to evolve into a broader platform for creative co-authoring. “Our big mission is to build a love of reading in every child,” he says. “In particular, we want to level the playing field in literacy and phonics for children from lower-income backgrounds, and to move children away from over-stimulating, exploitatively gamified screen time that manipulates attention, towards experiences that are mindful and creative.”

“Working with Kyle has been a real pleasure. He came in with a strong creative vision but also a genuine curiosity about how AI actually works. It’s been exciting to see the product evolve so quickly and to support someone who’s so passionate about using AI for positive impact.”

Dr Jennifer Williams,
Associate Advisor for BridgeAI at The Alan Turing Institute

About Innovate UK BridgeAI

Innovate UK BridgeAI empowers UK businesses in high-growth sectors, driving productivity and economic growth through the adoption of Artificial Intelligence. We bridge the gap between developers and end-users, fostering user-driven AI technologies.

With a focus on ethics, transparency and data privacy, we aim to build trust and confidence in the development of AI solutions. Strengthening AI leadership, supporting workforces, and promoting responsible innovation, BridgeAI shapes a collaborative and AI-enabled future.

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This work is led by **Dr Vera Matser**, Head of Strategic Capabilities and Principal Investigator for BridgeAI at The Alan Turing Institute.

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